

GAME CHANGER

Skills for your CV

This handout is designed to help you reflect on the skills you have developed over the Game Changer Challenge, and how you might articulate examples of how you have used these skills.

1. CHARACTER (how to behave & engage in the world):

Adaptability:

Consistently adapting to changing circumstances & environments, and embracing new ideas is one of the key characteristics of Design Thinking. Innovation in its nature is unpredictable and therefore you are constantly challenged to rethink and dare to go in new direction.

- Examples:
 - Working in new teams, meeting new people, working together to complete the tasks

Social & Cultural Awareness:

Design Thinking provides a framework for interdisciplinary collaboration, as its core is a “we-culture” of mutual creation. Diversity does not only get tolerated but promoted as being a crucial part of the process. You work together with people that are different from yourself. Consequently, you are consistently confronted with and learn more about new perspectives and points of view.

- Examples:
 - Working with new teams and with people from different disciplines
 - Assumption storming – looking at the world from a different point of view and learning about empathy for the end-user

2. SKILLS (how to use the knowledge you have gained):

Critical Thinking/ Problem Solving:

Design Thinking is a human-centred approach toward problem solving. It provides you with a framework of how to tackle complex problems. It reminds you to always be a questioning thinker as it prompts you to examine and test propositions of any kind which are offered for acceptance

- Examples:
 - Looking at the world through different lenses and asking who/ what/ where/ why, then doing further research to frame the challenge statement/ choose a detail to solve

Creativity:

Creative confidence requires creativity. Design thinking helps you apply, explore and practice creativity. It prompts you to use both of your hemispheres, meaning logical as well as the intuitive side of your brain. As an open-ended and playful approach, Design Thinking gives you the necessary freedom to be an explorer of the unknown.

- Examples:
 - Ideation - building on the ideas of others
 - Storyboarding/ creating a pitch to bring an idea to life

Collaboration:

Complex problems can only be solved through collaboration among people with different skills, backgrounds and perspectives. Design thinking facilitates an alignment of team members' perspectives as they work towards the common goal of improving human lives. Consequently, team members have a structured process of joining forces to achieve the goals they set.

- Examples:
 - Working in a new team and understanding strengths/ backgrounds (and developing relationships over the programme)
 - Respecting, listening and building on each others' ideas, and working together to create the pitch

3. LEARNING TO LEARN (how to reflect on & adapt by continuing to learn & grow):

Curiosity & Motivation:

Curiosity and motivation play an essential role in Design Thinking. Design Thinking encourages you to acknowledge that you may know some things, but there is still so much to explore! You have to adopt a “beginners mindset” and explore things from different perspectives. Quite often it results in empathy that you build for end-users, and you become intrinsically motivated to improve their experiences.

- Examples:
 - Researching the problem and narrowing in on experiences within that to choose a detail to solve

Reflection:

Reflection is constructive questioning about what you do and why you do it, and then deciding about the next steps in the future. This is a central facet of the iterative working process in Design Thinking. You constantly get feedback from yourself, the team and the users.

- Examples:
 - Re-framing the problem following your research and empathy - reflecting on what is really important and what the real challenges are
 - Reflecting to share with others, and considering future iterations of your ideas through the storyboard/ pitch